

Analysis of Heat Transfer within an Annular Reactor

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Abstract

This study investigates heat transfer within an annular reactor. The reactor consists of a 10m concentric bar of diameter 100 mm within a pipe diameter of 150 mm. The endothermic chemical reactions of the bar create a uniform cooling flux of 20 kW/m^2 . The reactor cools 1300 K inlet air flowing at a rate of 0.1 to 0.5 kg/s. ANSYS Fluent, a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software, was used to analyse the effects of mass flow rate, temperature dependent thermophysical properties, mesh refinement and turbulence models on the reactor's outlet and walls. It was found that the use of dynamic air properties and the correct turbulence model significantly improved results of the simulation.

1 Introduction

Annular heat transfer pipes are employed in a wide range of applications. These include, but are not limited to, cooling systems for nuclear reactors, gas turbines, and electric motors, as well as reactors designed for chemical processing involving both endothermic and exothermic reactions. [1]

Figure 1: The annular geometry of the heat exchanger.

The reactor is axially symmetric, meaning the geometry can be simplified into a 2D plane. This reduces the required computing power and is a common industry practice to improve computational efficiency. [2]

2 Mathematical Model and Computational Settings (Methodology)

2.1 Overview of CFD

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) in ANSYS Fluent involves solving the governing equations of fluid motion, primarily the Navier-Stokes equations [Appendix A], using finite-volume methods. Hydrodynamic models are used to simulate fluid flow, while additional mass transfer models can account for species transport or chemical reactions. The geometry is defined using a meshed computational domain that reflects the physical system. Geometrical simplifications and symmetry assumptions are often applied to reduce computational load. The selection of turbulence models, boundary conditions, and solver settings is based on the flow regime and desired accuracy of the simulation.

2.2 Simulation Setup

Initial simulations were conducted using the standard $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model, which is widely used for internal flows due to its balance between precision and computational efficiency. The intensity of the turbulence and the hydrodynamic length at the inlet were estimated based on the inlet conditions. In subsequent investigations, $k-\omega$ and Reynolds's Stress Model were used.

2.3 Mesh Design

A mesh-independent analysis was conducted on the simulation to determine a mesh that gives computational accuracy whilst also using the least amount of computational power possible [3]. Both hydraulic length and outlet temperature were used to determine an optimal mesh as shown in Figure 2. From the data shown, a mesh of 49000 elements was chosen (1400x35). From the geometry of the simulation, it is clear to see that the solutions near the boundary conditions (inner & outer wall, inlet & outlet) are the most computationally intensive, so a bias of 5 towards the boundary was chosen for all meshes to increase the mesh density at the important locations. Also, an x-y ratio of 40:1 was chosen for all meshes to make sure that the analysis was ratio-independent. The mesh analysis calculations were done with a flow rate of 5 kg/s .

Figure 2: Convergence of the hydraulic length and outlet temperature as the used mesh becomes finer.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Changing Physical Air Properties

The first investigation was based on how changing the physical properties of air from constant to dynamic would affect the outcome of the simulation. For this investigation, the thermophysical properties of air were set to constant values and dynamic equations as shown in Table 1.

Air Property	Const Values	Dynamic Equations (K)
Density, ρ (kg/m ³)	Incompressible Ideal Gas	Incompressible Ideal Gas
Specific Heat Capacity, C_p (J/(kg K))	1021.5	$4 \times 10^{-5}T^2 + 0.093248T + 982.0204$
Thermal Conductivity, k (W/(mK))	0.025959	$-1.65 \times 10^{-8}T^2 + 7.449395 \times 10^{-5}T + 0.00518306$
Viscosity, μ (kg/(ms))	1.832×10^{-5}	$-1.645 \times 10^{-11}T^2 + 5.302664 \times 10^{-8}T + 4.213124 \times 10^{-6}$
Molecular Weight (kg/kmol)	28.966 [4]	28.966 [4]

Table 1: The values and equations used for the constant and dynamic physical properties of air

Having air properties fixed at 300K (Room temperature) rather than 1300K (Inlet air temperature) is a big simplification in the model. Because of this, the expected result is that the simulations of constant air properties will cool slower due to the lower C_p , μ and k .

(a) Temperature distribution on the Bar wall (Uniform cooling flux $\dot{Q} = 20W/m^2$)

(b) Temperature distribution on the Pipe wall (Uniform cooling flux $\dot{Q} = 0W/m^2$)

Figure 3: The cooling of the air for different flow rates at both walls of the annular space.

The cooling rate along the reactor is shown by the gradient of temperature distribution. The lower flow rates cool significantly more than the higher flow rates. As the heat flux through the bar is a constant $20kW/m^2$, the slower flow rates cause the air to spend an extended period in the reactor, and so there is more time for turbulent mixing of the air and thus more cooling.

Figure 3.a shows that the fluid with dynamic properties has a higher outlet temperature. This is because the bar wall has a constant cooling flux which lowers the temperature of the air closest to the wall; in turn this reduces the thermal conductivity (k) and the specific heat capacity (C_p). The drop of thermal conductivity leads to a reduction in the rate of heat transfer through the fluid.

Figure 3.b shows clear indications that for the slower flow rates, the temperature boundary increases faster, as the pipe takes longer to see any cooling effect for the faster flow rates. This is because for slower flow rates, the time the air is in contact with the wall is extended, allowing more heat to diffuse into the air, leading to a steeper temperature gradient and thus a thicker boundary layer.

The use of dynamic fluid properties leads to more accurate heat transfer modeling, this is most apparent in the thermal and viscous boundary layers which show the steepest temperature and velocity gradients. This demonstrates that the thermal boundary layers grow faster for the dynamic air, but the cooling rate at the pipe wall is less, as illustrated by the divergence of the dotted and solid lines in Figure 3.b.

Figure 4: The data for the exhaust air leaving the annular space of the reactor

Figure 4.b shows many of the simulation parameters at work. For example all flow rates and fluid properties, at both 0.05m and 0.075m, show the no-slip boundary condition ($V = 0m/s^2$) [5]. Also evident is that the velocity profiles are symmetric around the 0.0625m line for constant air properties, typical for laminar flow in a pipe. However, the velocity profiles are skewed away from the bar wall for dynamic air properties. This asymmetrical profile is due to the higher viscosity and density in the cooler air, which increases the flow resistance at the bar wall.

Only one of the walls contributes to the cooling of the air, this is shown by the outlet temperature data (Figure 4.a). The rate of cooling is highest at the Bar wall (0.05m) as shown by the very sharp temperature gradient. This graph highlights the importance of using dynamic air properties, as the ability of the air to conduct heat varies throughout the different regions of the model, giving large variations in temperature by the cooled wall at the outlet. The difference between the constant and dynamic thermophysical properties of air can be more clearly seen in Appendix B.

3.2 Investigation of Different Turbulence Models

For any CFD problem, there are a variety of different turbulence models available. It is imperative for the accuracy of the solution that the best turbulence model is selected. However, much like mesh refinement, models that give better results can cause an increase in computational work.

The models investigated are the K- ϵ model, the K- ω and the Reynolds Stress Model (RSM). Both the K- ϵ and K- ω models solve two separate transport equations using dissipation rate (ϵ) and specific dissipation rate (ω), respectively. The RSM model directly solves the transport equations for each component of the Reynolds' stress tensor.

From the output of the simulations, specifically Figures 5.a and 6.a, the RSM consistently predicts a lower temperature, stronger heat transfer and thinner thermal boundary layer. This suggests that the RSM has stronger turbulent mixing of the fluid than the other two tested models. It is important to note that for RSM simulations, despite there not being an optimal Y^+ value, reducing Y^+ as much as possible leads to more accurate results, and this model has the lowest Y^+ of all models tested. RSM also has the most insulated core, shown in Figure 6.a. This insulation of the core comes from the turbulence anisotropy, an effect due to the modeling near the walls of the model and the large thermal gradient.

(a) Temperature distribution on the Bar and Pipe wall for different turbulence models

(b) Y^+ distribution along the Bar and Pipe wall for different turbulence models

Figure 5: Distributions along the two walls of the reactor.

Generally, the $K-\epsilon$ and $K-\omega$ models follow similar profiles. This is expected as, on a mathematical level, they are solving the same equations. A large difference in the models is their optimal Y^+ values, with $K-\omega$ working best at $Y^+ \approx 1$, whereas $K-\epsilon$ gives useful and stable results at values as high as $Y^+ > 30$ [6]. From the simulations, we see extreme regions of error at 5m and 9m for $K-\omega$ due to the large Y^+ value, which causes regions of separation and reattachment of the flow at the pipe and bar wall. This sequential separation and reattachment give rise to the oscillation in error that can be seen in Figure 5. Despite this, at the outlet, the errors do not have a dominating effect, and the profiles seen from both $K-\epsilon$ and $K-\omega$ are very similar with the average outlet temperatures being within 0.05% of each other.

(a) Temperature distribution at the outlet for different turbulence models

(b) Velocity distribution at the outlet for different turbulence models

Figure 6: The data for different models at the exit of the simulation

4 Conclusion and Future Improvements

The CFD simulations effectively modeled heat transfer within the annular reactor, capturing the influence of the mass flow rate, the variation of thermophysical properties, and the selection of the turbulence model on the outlet temperature and the cooling performance of the wall. The results clearly demonstrated that using dynamic air properties provided more accurate and physically representative outcomes, particularly in the development of boundary layers and the asymmetry of the velocity profiles. Lower flow rates were found to enhance cooling efficiency as a result of increased residence time and thermal mixing.

To improve the accuracy and realism of the model, future work could include incorporating radiation heat transfer, particularly given the high inlet air temperature of 1300 K. A transient simulation could also capture time-dependent behavior and unsteady thermal effects. Furthermore, validating the model against experimental or literature data would further strengthen its reliability. Exploring alternative turbulence models, such as the SST $k-\omega$ or Reynolds Stress Model (RSM), may also yield improved predictions in near-wall regions. Finally, adaptive meshing around steep temperature gradients could improve resolution without significantly increasing computational cost.

References

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Appendix A Governing Equations

Energy balance equation rearranged for outlet temperature:

$$T_{\text{out}} = T_{\text{in}} + \frac{\dot{Q}}{\dot{m}C_p} \quad (1)$$

where: T_{out} is the outlet temperature, T_{in} is the inlet temperature, \dot{Q} is the rate of heat added to the control volume, \dot{m} is the mass flow rate, and C_p is the specific heat at constant pressure.

The Navier-Stokes equations are fundamental equations that describe fluid motion, derived from Newton's second law of motion, expressing the conservation of momentum.

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \vec{V}}{\partial t} + \vec{V} \cdot \nabla \vec{V} \right) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \vec{V} + \vec{f} \quad (2)$$

where: ρ is the fluid density, t is time, \vec{V} is the fluid velocity vector, ∇ is the differential operator, p is pressure, μ is dynamic viscosity, and \vec{f} represents body forces (e.g. gravity).

Conservation of Energy Equation

$$\rho C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T \right) = k \nabla^2 T + \Phi \quad (3)$$

where: ρ is the fluid density, C_p is the specific heat at constant pressure, T is temperature, t is time, \vec{V} is the fluid velocity vector, ∇ is the differential operator, k is thermal conductivity, and Φ is the viscous dissipation function.

Appendix B Constant and Dynamic Air Difference Diagrams

(a) Difference in temperature profiles between constant and dynamic air alone the pipe wall

(b) Difference in velocity profiles between constant and dynamic air at the outlet

Figure 7: Difference plots between constant and dynamic air.